

HowTo: Reporting in Initialisation

Created by Dorian Lehmenkühler | Last updated April 2026

Purpose of this document

This document provides some additional guidance on the reporting that should be done during and by the end of the service initialisation phase. It complements the more formal [Requirements for Completion of Initialisation Phase](#) and focuses on how to actually create the reports.

Documentation: What and where

During the initialisation phase you will need to report your progress twice: Once in the application for the next phase, service integration, and once as a final report¹ when you are at the end of the initialisation phase. Both reports will be based on the same tracking of your progress in OpenProject (OP), which should be continuously updated to reflect the current status of your service. Details on this will be explained in the [next section](#), but the OP workspace will be provided to you and already contain the relevant work packages for each of the [initialisation phase deliverables](#) relevant to your service.

For your integration proposal, which is due after about six months in initialisation, the [integration template](#) requires a description of the current status for each of the [initialisation phase deliverables](#). You should therefore [export the current status](#) of the deliverables D.Ini.1-7 from OP and attach them to the proposal. In the proposal itself the service can then be described briefly on a higher level: What is the current state of the service, how far has it come and what are the key points you have achieved? For all further explanations you can then refer to the detailed exported OP report in the appendix of the proposal.

In addition a final report for all initialisation phase deliverables is required to [formally complete the initialisation](#). The integration phase can be started independently if it is funded. With a sufficiently up-to-date OP, where all results are described in their work packages, this will reduce itself to marking the corresponding tasks in the OP as completed and exporting them.

¹ Technically, D.Ini.1 to D.Ini.3 are a report and for D.Ini.4-7 documentation on what was done is required, but for the scope of this document this leads to the exact same tasks and is synonymous.

In summary you should document:

OpenProject	Integration Proposal
Tangible results, work in progress, detailed progress of tasks, next steps and documentation (all either directly in OP, or linked to an Base4NFDI-accessible external resource, like Zenodo)	High-level overview of the status of the service as stated in the template, key points you achieved so far and outlook on what you expect to get done by the end of initialisation

OpenProject Reporting

Reporting in OpenProject takes place inside the work packages (alias tasks, alias tickets) in your service workspace. For each deliverable, a corresponding work package will be provided right at the start of your initialisation phase. Figure 1 shows an example of how that might look. If you chose in your proposal to have your deliverables additional to the initialisation phase ones, you should map/link your own Milestones/Deliverables/Work Packages to these ones, so you know which work will go into which part of the report right from the start. For this, open a work package and select the 'Relations' tab on the right. There you can 'create a new relation' and select your other existing work packages, linking them to the work package you are editing. Additionally these relations can also be put into the description field, so they appear in an export.

ID ↑	↳ SUBJECT	TYPE	STATUS	PRIORITY
10687	Measure 1.1: Coordination and coherent service landscape	MEASURE	In progress	Normal
10698	Measure 1.2: Support for user-driven requirements analysis, piloting and t...	MEASURE	In progress	Normal
10705	Measure 1.3 (M1.3): Support for service (component) evaluation, design a...	MEASURE	In progress	Normal
10711	Measure 1.4: Service initialisation (flex-funds)	MEASURE	In progress	Normal
12005	Working Space TA1	PHASE	In progress	Normal
14612	Reporting (template for new services)	PHASE	In progress	Normal
14613	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.2: Documentation of evaluation of existing softwar...	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal
14614	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.3: Documentation of service design	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal
14615	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.6: Presentation of your results	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal
14617	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.4: Service prototype	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal
14618	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.5: Service piloting and user testing	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal
14619	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.1: Documentation of requirements analysis	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal
15120	TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.7: Participation in Base4NFDI outreach events	TASK	To be scheduled	Normal

Figure 1: Example view of the work packages for deliverables in initialisation phase. Note that the TA 1 deliverables are grouped separately under 'Reporting'.

For each work package you can track status, priority, assignee and percent of completion. The most important thing for the reports is the description field though, where you describe your progress and results. A detailed explanation on the actual items that should be documented there can be found in the aforementioned [Requirements for Completion](#). Each work packages' description is also pre-filled with the respective section from these requirements. For example, the work package for D.Ini.1 should look similar to what is shown in Figure 2. The description field is the free text field at the top of the work package and its text can just be replaced by your actual contents including e.g. visualisations.

Parent: [Reporting \(template for new services\)](#) ✎ ✕

TASK TODO4NFDI / D.Ini.1: Documentation of requirements analysis

To be scheduled ▼ #14619: Created by Dorian Lehmenkühler-Base4NFDI. Last updated on 21.04.2026 08:00.

Requirements Analysis (D.Ini.1)

- Provide a summary of requirements from the consortia for a basic service on your specific topic.
- Provide an overview of the expectations formulated by the consortia in the relevant working group on the topic and which part of these expectations the proposed solution fulfils.
 - If applicable, also indicate the methodology used (e.g. survey).
- Define the target group(s) for the service and their use cases. Describe the benefits for each target group.
- The report for this deliverable is due 3 months after the start date

Link your related Deliverables in the 'Relations' tab.

> Need guidance?

- Plomin, J., & Kuper, S. (2025). Base4NFDI-Toolkit for Requirements Analysis Strategy (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17245694>
- Manske, A., Plomin, J., Lorenz, A.-L., & Kuper, S. (2025, January 9). Base4NFDI - Persona Creation Kit. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14621170>
- Kuper, S., & Plomin, J. (2025). Base4NFDI – User Story Guide (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14998462>

Figure 2: Example view of the work package for the initialisation phase deliverable D.Ini.1. The description field is pre-filled with guidance on which kind of content should be provided, taken from the Requirements for Completion, where they can also be looked up at any time (if you choose to delete them here).

If you have documentation or results published at an external place (e.g. Zenodo), please link it here (there is no need to copy anything of it verbatim). When everything is ready, you can [export the report](#).

Additional Considerations

When looking at these deliverables, you might notice that you may already have done some or even much work in these areas for the proposal to start the initialisation phase. You are free to re-use as much of that as you like here! The reports are there to ensure that each aspect is considered in sufficient depth and in a standardised way during the initialisation, and also to provide a chance to revisit your initial findings and thoughts, and to harmonise, adjust, back them up with additional data, and in the best case, publish them, e.g. on Zenodo.

Furthermore, not every deliverable might be phrased in a way that fits perfectly to the goals of your service, especially if you're not developing software yourself (yet). The idea for reporting then is to interpret the deliverables in a most meaningful way. For example, if you use an existing software solution, in D.Ini.3 you should describe how you will operate this service inside Base4NFDI and how you will adapt it to the NFDI community.

For any remaining questions, please have a look at the [Requirements for Completion of Initialisation Phase](#) and reach out to the [TA1 team](#) or your [service steward](#)!